

EXPLORING THE LIGHT-WEIGHTING POTENTIAL OF STEEL REINFORCED WITH FRP

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ABSTRACT

In the drive for light-weighting in many industries, optimum material selection is at the forefront of research. The use and study of fibre reinforced composite (FRP) materials and light-weight metallics is especially prominent. It is widely recognised however that the continued use of steel has many advantages including cost, ease of fabrication and recyclability. A light-weighting opportunity exists for creating hybrids of steel and FRP possibly providing a solution to the ever increasing pressures exerted on automotive designers. Reinforcing steel with composites is not unknown. In many industries, aging metallic structures are already in use. Replacing them would be a costly and inefficient way of dealing with this aging (cracking, corrosion, wear, etc.), and retrospective reinforcement techniques using composites are sometimes used. This paper focuses on the characterisation of high strength automotive grade steel with a fibre reinforced polyamide (PA6 GF60) laminate. Initial characterisation of this hybrid was done by quasi-static three point bend testing on coupons of two thicknesses of steel. Using LS-DYNA, a model was created and validated against the mechanical testing results. The opportunity for down gauging of the steel has been shown in the mechanical testing as well as with the model, opening a wide range of applications. It has been found hybrids offer a 40 % increase in specific stiffness with respect to steel only. The project is ongoing and will continue to investigate an automotive substructure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel has historically been the material of choice for Body-In-White (BIW), with aluminium and Fibre Reinforced Plastic (FRP) materials making a later appearance [1]. The use of FRP in BIW has up to recently mainly been present in the predominantly niche market of sports cars, in part due to the high costs [2]. However, this use is now extending, through developments such as the BMW i3 and i8, to a more generalised use [3]. Ever increasing demand for body light-weighting [4 – 8] drives the concept of combining the strength provided by either ultra-high strength steel (UHSS) or advanced high strength steel (AHSS) and the comparatively light FRP to achieve a desired mass reduction whilst keeping the overall performance – and ideally cost – unchanged. It is of interest also to use a composite with a thermoplastic matrix, as this would contribute towards the recyclability and End-of-Life targets.

Studies/state of the art of research highlight the versatility of and opportunities presented by FRP reinforced structures, with a wide range of substrates being reinforced. In the largest proportion of cases, this reinforcement is retrospective [9], highlighting an opportunity to approach the design stage using the FRP/substrate as a material in its own right. Most of the work has a focus on the strength or load bearing capacity/buckling of the elements [10].

Bruno Ludke [11], BMW Body Design specialist, identified four areas for critical consideration: structural dynamics, static stiffness, crashworthiness, weight optimization. He developed a lightweight design material criterion for bending stiffness [12]

$$\text{Bending stiffness criterion: } \frac{\sqrt[3]{E}}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where E is the Young's Modulus, and ρ the density.

RWTH Aachen University in conjunction with VW and Daimler AG and funded by the Forschungsvereinigung Automobiltechnik i.e. (FAT) has researched the lightweight approach in which the sheet thickness of metals is reduced and local reinforcements of FRP (both GFRP and CFRP) are added to compensate for the weakening of the structure [13]. The analysis was carried out on the floor structure of a representative middle class vehicle, specifically the rear tunnel bridge, the seat cross members, and the front and rear supports, as well as the floor long members. The materials used were PA 6.6 CFRP and PA 6 GFRP for composites and micro alloyed galvanized high strength steels (minimum yield strength from 260 to 340 MPa). Using the simulation model available from the SuperLightCar program [14], the reference behaviour of the structure was obtained. Using Optistruct and LS-DYNA (MAT_058) as simulation software, “the analysis of 120 variations with adaption and optimisation of the parameter sheet thickness, laminate thickness of the FRP elements as well as number, position and length of the reinforcing elements, lead to a lightweight floor structure, where through the use of 1 kg CFRP/GFRP a total weight reduction of 2 kg was achieved. This corresponds to a weight reduction of 22 %.” [13]. A 10 % reduction in vehicle mass leads to fuel savings up from 5 to 10 % [12].

The paper presented here is a fundamental study aiming to understand the potential for light weighting presented by the use of this hybrid materials. Specifically, it studies the stiffness properties in the elastic region of the combined FRP and high strength steel hybrid by conducting a series of basic experiments in bending.

This data is used as an input towards the finite element simulation, in order to create a model with a high degree of stability and confidence. The model is provided as a tool for further investigation into the potential of light-weighting using the intelligent deployment of composite material on a steel structure.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Preparation of specimens / Material Properties/Experimental Program

The material properties that affect stiffness and weight are the material density ρ and Young's modulus E [12].

This research concentrates on high strength steels, specifically DP600, a cold rolled Dual Phase steel with martensitic dispersion in a soft ferrite matrix [15]. The DP600, provided by industrial sponsor Tata Steel, has been studied extensively and its properties, summarised in Table 1, are well known [16].

Engineering constant		Identification
<i>Stiffness</i>	[GPa]	205
<i>Poisson's ratio</i>	–	0.3
<i>Yield Strength</i>	[MPa]	355
<i>UTS</i>	[MPa]	600+
ρ	[kg/m ³]	7850

Table 1: DP600 properties obtained from tensile tests following standard BS EN ISO 6892-1 (2009).

The thicknesses of DP600 used were 0.8 mm and 0.5 mm. As the coating of the steel affects its surface energy and therefore the bonding potential, the steel used in these experiments was uncoated. It was preserved from rust with an oil-based layer which was easily removed in surface preparation with the use of a solvent. The surface of the steel was mechanically roughened and cleaned in preparation for the adhesive bonding. A number of trials and literature studies [17] showed this to provide the best bond. The steel was also lightly heated to approximately 60°C to facilitate the spreading of the adhesive.

Where the hybrid fabrication was concerned, the bonding of the composite to the steel was done using an Alpha Adhesive one-part epoxy based resin, SAS 272, which cured when heated at 150°C.

The thermoplastic used was a PA6 GF60 purchased from Ticona, with well documented properties within WMG [18]. This is a pre-impregnated polyamide 6 matrix with continuous glass fibres at $V_f = 60\%$, $T_m = 235\text{ °C}$; additional properties summarised in Table 2.

Engineering constant		Identification
E_1	[GPa]	35
E_2	[GPa]	6.8
ν_{12}	–	0.36
G_{12}	[GPa]	2
ρ	[kg/m ³]	1720

Table 2: PA6 GF60 properties obtained from in-house tests.

In this specific production of hybrid samples, 4 layers of PA6 GF60 were consolidated and cured under vacuum at between 235 °C and 240 °C for 10 minutes. Three different balanced layups were considered, [0,90][90,0], [45,-45][-45,45] and [90,0][0,90]. The standard ply directionality used for this work is depicted in Figure 1. This composite layer was then cured off in conjunction with the DP600 and SAS 272 adhesive at 150°C for 60 minutes. The composite surface was prepared for adhesion using a peel-ply during the consolidation phase.

The samples were cut to size, to a length of 60 mm and width of 15 mm.

2.2 Instrumentation/Set up

Quasi-static testing was performed using a 100 kN Instron Universal Tensile Testing machine, set up in compression using a three point bending fixture.

Image 1: Three point bend test rig and fixture set up

According to standards BS EN ISO 14125:1998, the speed was set at:

$$v = 1 \text{ mm/min} \quad (2)$$

In order to ensure a high confidence level in the result, each test was repeated five times.

The samples were tested both in a case of composite over steel (composite/steel) and steel over composite (steel/composite), where the loading path in the material is different, specifically in the fibres, either in compression or in tension.

Image 2: Three point bend fixture set up with composite/steel and steel/composite

3 SIMULATION PROGRAM

3.1 Software/Assumptions/Preparation

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is the widely accepted method to predict the performance of a known material under specific circumstances and perform a sensitivity or parametric analysis on the variables. Here the FEA package used is the commercially available LS DYNA.

Based on the assumption that the adhesive bond between the PA6GF60 and the DP600 is perfect in the elastic region, the simulations were performed in the LS DYNA solver, using PART_COMPOSITE, MAT_58 Laminated Composite Fabric for the PA6GF60 and MAT_2 Orthotropic Elastic for the DP600. Figures 1, 2 and 3 depict the ply directionality in testing and simulation.

Figure 1: Composite/Steel [0,90][90,0] ply directionality – not to scale

Figure 1 depicts the composite/steel situation of the [0,90][90,0] layup, where the fibres on the outer layers of composite run parallel to the length of the specimens and the loading paths.

Figure 2: Composite/Steel [90,0][0,90] ply directionality – not to scale

Figure 2 depicts the composite/steel situation on the [90,0][0,90] layup, where the fibres on the outer layers of the composite run perpendicular to the length of the specimens and the loading paths.

Figure 3: Composite/Steel [45,-45][-45,45] ply directionality – not to scale

Figure 3 depicts the composite/steel situation on the [45,-45][-45,45] layup, where the fibres on the outer layers of the composite run at 45° to the specimen length and the loading paths.

The experimental results validate the simulation results and provide confidence in the material model developed and the assumptions made. The fibre orientation in the composite was checked using optical microscopy to insure total coherence between the experimental and simulated set ups. Image 3 shows the microscopic image of the [0,90][90,0] layup.

Image 3: Optical microscopy image of a sample cross section of the [0,90][90,0] layup

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Figures 4 and 5 show the flexure load – flexure extension summaries for the samples tested. In figure 4, the loads are seen to start above 0, this is due to the pre-loading of the specimens in the testing machine. Figure 5 shows the correlation between the tested flexure and the simulated one for the case of the 0.8 mm DP600 with all three ply combinations PA6 GF60. The test curves were shifted to the origin for better comparison with simulated curves. These cases are presented as an illustration of the level of correlation between the testing and simulation. The slopes of the corresponding test-FE curves matches very well for the [0,90][90,0] and [90,0][0,90] composite layup situations. In the case of the [45,-45][−45,45], the small discrepancy seen in figure 5 is due to a shift of the specimen in the test environment. The samples were consistently seen to rotate in alignment to the fibre direction.

Figure 4: Load – extension summary graph for the elastic region

Figure 5: Example of correlation between tested and simulated flexure load – extension data for the elastic region

Figure 6 shows the specific bending stiffness of the materials, according to Ludke’s light-weight design material criterion for bending stiffness expressed in equation (1).

Despite the situations of composite/steel and steel/composite being tested separately, their performance difference in the elastic region is negligible and this difference has been added to the standard deviation.

Figure 6: Normalised specific Bending Stiffness of benchmark DP600 and hybrid samples

Elastic analysis using beam bending theory was applied to the results.

$$E = \frac{Force}{Deflection} \frac{L^3}{48 I} \quad (3)$$

$$E = \frac{1}{4} k \frac{L^3}{bd^3} \quad (4)$$

where k is the slope of the elastic region of the force – deflection curve, L is the span length, b is the breadth and d is the depth. From this elastic analysis, a weight save potential was calculated. This is based on an identical performance, ie, k is constant. These results are displayed in Table 3 below, and show the definite potential of light weighting using FRP to reinforce steel.

Material	% Increase in specific stiffness	% weight save for equivalent performance
<i>Steel DP600</i>	-	-
<i>0.5 mm DP600</i>	[0,90][90,0]	44
	[45,-45][-45,45]	15
	[90,0][0,90]	33
<i>0.8 mm DP600</i>	[0,90][90,0]	26
	[45,-45][-45,45]	8
	[90,0][0,90]	20

Table 3: Percentage increase in specific bending stiffness and percentage weight save

4.2 Discussion

Set up as an iteration loop the testing and simulation results were used to counter-validate each

other. Using two different thicknesses of steel and six different fibre orientations and layups, and repeatable results in the experimental section, it was possible to create a model with a high degree of confidence.

There is a good agreement between the results from the experimental and simulation program, providing confidence in the material model and assumptions made and allowing for the development and analysis of non-experimentally tested situations. The simulation results are consistent to within a 10 % of the experimental results, in every case an over-prediction. This is attributed to the experimental uncertainty (machine lag) and approximations made in the extraction of the test data from the testing machine.

This high degree of correlation between the simulation and the testing reinforces the confidence in the validation and opens the possibility of using this model for a purpose filling application.

The greatest increase in specific bending stiffness is 44 %, translating to a maximum weight saving potential of 30 %. This is a large enough potential for the concept to be investigated on a larger scale, as this weight save is expected to be lessened/diluted when applied in a situation where reinforced sections cohabit with unreinforced sections.

The difference in performance based on the fibre directionality indicates opportunity available due to fibre orientation effect, where the composite can be tailored to the situation due to its anisotropic nature. Tailored composite patches are an option when dealing with a structure in need of light-weighting. Indeed, the simulation can be taken further into an optimization context, and expanded to composite materials that have a higher Young's modulus, as these are likely to present a higher weight saving potential overall.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The results and analysis lead to the following conclusions:

1. There is potential for using FRP to reinforce steel in an intelligent deployment of composite material
2. The increase in specific bending stiffness is 44 % when reinforcing with a balanced 4 layer GF60 PA6
3. For an identical stiffness performance, there is a potential 30 % weight save
4. The orientation of the outer layer of fibres affects the stiffness greatly
5. The potential for optimisation of a structure and light-weighting is present

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